

POLITICAL SCIENCES

A NEW STAGE OF RELATIONS BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN AND HUNGARY: STRATEGIC PARTNERSHIP AND TURKIC WORLD

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Abstract

Azerbaijan and Hungary, possessing unique geopolitical and economic positions, over the past decades have managed to turn their relations into a strategic partnership, which covers such key areas as politics, economics, energy, culture and the humanitarian sphere. In the face of global challenges, as energy security and new forms of economic interaction come to the fore, relations between the two countries take on a new dimension. Over the past years, Azerbaijan and Hungary have shown an example of a dynamic and constructive dialogue at the highest level. Notable is the fact that Hungary is an observer in the Organization of Turkic States. Since the beginning of the 2020s, several key visits of Azerbaijani President Ilham Aliyev to Hungary and Hungarian Prime Minister Viktor Orban to Azerbaijan have taken place, which have played an important role in strengthening political ties.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Hungary, Trans-Adriatic Gas Corridor [TAP], Organization of Turkic States.

Introduction

In the modern system of international relations, the deepening of interstate cooperation is determined not only by geographical proximity and economic interests, but also by common values, historical ties and mutually beneficial strategic cooperation. In the context of a changing international order, Azerbaijan's foreign policy priorities necessitate strong cooperation with both global players and regional centers of power. Independent Azerbaijan develops mutually beneficial relations with neighboring and distant states in various fields, both bilaterally and multilaterally. In this sense, the relations that have developed between Azerbaijan and Hungary are exemplary. The development of bilateral and multilateral cooperation with Hungary, a strategic partner of Azerbaijan and one of the most reliable partners in the European Union, is one of the main directions of our country's foreign policy. Taking similar positions both in the region and on international platforms, our states over time not only strengthened friendly relations, but also formed a multifaceted model of cooperation based on strategic partnership.

In this sense, the relations that have developed between Azerbaijan and Hungary are exemplary. It should be noted that diplomatic relations between the two countries were established in 1992. In 2004, the Embassy of Azerbaijan was opened in Hungary, and in 2009 - the Embassy of Hungary in our country. Inter-parliamentary ties between our friendly countries are also developing at a high level. A working group on Azerbaijani-Hungarian inter-parliamentary relations operates in Parliament (Milli Majlis). Dozens of documents signed so far between the two countries play an important role in strengthening the legal framework. The Joint Strategic Partnership Declaration, signed in 2014, is essential to the development of our relationship. Azerbaijani-Hungarian cooperation was further strengthened with the signing of the Joint Declaration on Expanded Strategic Partnership in 2023.

Relationship Root: A Values-Based Partnership

Although Azerbaijani-Hungarian relations were established in 1992, their strategic nature has become

noticeable in the last decade. The Joint Declaration on Strategic Partnership, signed in 2014, and its expanded version in 2023 became not just a diplomatic act, but a conceptual framework expressing the mutual interests and long-term intentions of the two states. The range of cooperation - from energy security to education and the humanitarian sphere - demonstrates the depth of this partnership. Regular mutual visits and meetings of heads of state played an indispensable role in bringing these relations to a high level.

The parties make a unique contribution to geopolitical relations, based on the principles of sovereignty, equality and non-interference in internal affairs, as well as supporting each other within the framework of international organizations. The fact that Hungary is one of the countries supporting Azerbaijan's interests in the European Union creates important diplomatic support for our republic's efforts to integrate into Europe.

On February 18, 2008, the Joint Statement of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the President of Hungary was signed, which emphasized support for the fundamental principles and norms of the Charter of the United Nations, the Helsinki Final Act and the principles of international law, such as sovereignty, territorial integrity and inviolability of state borders. The parties announced their entry into a strategic partnership in order to strengthen relations by deepening and expanding cooperation between the two countries in areas of mutual interest, both bilaterally and multilaterally. The Joint Statement indicated:

- creation of a Strategic Dialogue to discuss bilateral relations, as well as global and regional issues of mutual interest;

- enhanced cooperation in the United Nations, including its specialized agencies and institutions, OSCE, Council of Europe, as well as on issues related to the EU, NATO and other international and regional forums, etc. [2]

In November 2014, the Joint Declaration "On Strategic Partnership between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Hungary" was signed, which also pointed to joint initiatives on important regional

and international issues, of common interest, to promote links between foreign policy think tanks and research institutes with a view to enhancing exchanges and facilitating their cooperation, intensifying their efforts to peacefully resolve conflicts in the world and strengthen international peace and security." [1]

Signed in Budapest in 2023, the Declaration on Strategic Partnership further strengthened the legal and political framework for this relationship. In a press statement during his working visit to Hungary, President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Ilham Aliyev praised the relations between the two countries, saying that Azerbaijan and Hungary are friendly countries, strategic partners, and stressed that relations are further strengthened, while recalling that relations between Baku and Budapest are based on historical traditions and unshakable friendship: "Once again, we saw that our positions on many issues coincide. Signed in Budapest in 2023 When we look at the processes taking place today in a changing world, there is no big difference in our positions. One of the similarities is that Hungary is landlocked. Azerbaijan is also one of these countries. Yes, we are located on the coast of the Caspian Sea, but we also have no access to the open seas." [5]

Joint participation in such global events as COP29, cooperation in the field of energy, transport, culture, defense and law, outlines the contours of a new geopolitical model.

Inter-parliamentary ties between the two countries are also developing successfully. Mutual visits of members of the Azerbaijan-Hungary Working Group on Inter-Parliamentary Relations and the Hungarian-Azerbaijan Inter-Parliamentary Friendship Group are regular. Close cooperation is maintained within the framework of international parliamentary organizations [8].

Energy - geopolitical bridge and strategic pillar

Energy cooperation with Hungary confirms Azerbaijan's growing role in the European energy market. The energy cooperation relations formed between Azerbaijan and Hungary are currently reaching a strategic level. As President Ilham Aliyev noted, Hungarian companies participate in the main oil and gas projects of Azerbaijan - Azeri-Chirag-Guneshli and Shahdeniz. [6] This is not only an economic interest, but also an indicator of a long-term partnership based on mutual trust. The resource base of Azerbaijani gas is quite extensive and expanding, new gas fields will be commissioned. Today Azerbaijan exports natural gas to 12 countries. 10 of them are European countries, and 8 are members of the European Union [7]. The European Commission recognizes Azerbaijan as a pan-European gas supplier and a reliable partner. The commissioning of new gas fields, the expansion of the geography of natural gas exports and the status of a pan-European supplier further strengthen the role of Azerbaijan in the field of energy security. In particular, the planned projects in the field of green energy - 6 thousand megawatts of production capacity - serve both to optimize domestic resources and contribute to the process of green transition in Europe. The next contract is supposed to be signed in 2026. The Hungarian company

will start working on the onshore oil fields of Azerbaijan. The operation of Azerbaijani natural gas to Hungary has been carried out since 2024. It was decided to organize gas supplies at the level of Hungary's needs. Azerbaijan is also actively working with Hungary in the field of green energy. It is planned to produce 6 thousand megawatts of green energy over the next five years, while 500 megawatts have been created over the past two years. Thus, only these projects will save about 3-4 billion cubic meters of gas [7].

Energy infrastructure stretching from the Caspian Sea through the Black Sea to Europe is not just a technological project, it is the result of trust, mutual confidence and political will between regions. Azerbaijan's energy exports are no longer limited to oil and gas, but also accelerate the transition to green energy. The agreement on strategic partnership in the field of green energy, signed in Bucharest by the governments of Azerbaijan, Hungary, Romania and Georgia, provides for the transfer of energy between our countries and the implementation of new energy projects. This initiative will also bring the huge wind power potential of the Caspian Sea to European markets and will further diversify Europe's energy security. These projects, in particular, the construction of an underwater power transmission line across the Black Sea, will increase the volume of energy transportation between Europe and Azerbaijan and will contribute to the use of renewable energy sources. We are also actively working with Hungary in the field of green energy. Azerbaijan has a very large-scale program in the field of green energy. Over the next five years, we will produce 6,000 megawatts of green energy. Over the past two years, 500 megawatts have been created, 6 thousand megawatts will be delivered within five years. Thus, only these projects will allow us to save about 3-4 billion cubic meters of gas, the main direction of supply, of course, will be Turkey and European countries. Cooperation in the energy sector is of particular importance. MOL Group owns a 9.57% stake in the Azeri-Chirag-Guneshli field and an 8.9% stake in the Baku-Tbilisi-Ceyhan pipeline project. The memorandum of understanding on cooperation in the field of natural gas between the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Trade of Hungary, signed in Budapest on January 30, 2023, laid the foundation for further success in this direction [5]. On June 2, 2023, an agreement was signed between the State Oil Company of the Republic of Azerbaijan (SOCAR) and the MVM group of companies on the sale of 100 million cubic meters of natural gas. On June 5, 2024, documents were signed with the MVM group of companies on the acquisition of a stake in the Shahdeniz project, and on September 20, documents on exploration, development and production at the Shamakha-Gobustan field were signed with the MOL group of companies.

As part of the Solidarity Ring initiative, on April 25, 2023, a memorandum of understanding was signed in Sofia between Bulgartransgaz (Bulgaria), Transgaz (Romania), FGSZ (Hungary), Eustream (Slovakia) and SOCAR.

The Government of Hungary supports the establishment of a green energy corridor based on the "Strategic Partnership Agreement for the Development and

Transfer of Green Energy between the Governments of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Georgia, Romania and Hungary."

Ally of economic growth: mutual investment and trade

The growth of trade and investment initiatives between the two countries indicates that cooperation is carried out not only at the state, but also at the business level. Projects implemented by Hungarian companies in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan, the construction of infrastructure facilities and educational institutions, are also a new stage in post-conflict diplomacy. This indicates that Hungary has been supporting the territorial integrity and sovereignty of Azerbaijan since the establishment of diplomatic relations and during the 44th day war. Trade relations in bilateral relations also demonstrate quite positive dynamics. Economic commissions operate between the two countries, business forums are held. Hungarian companies show great interest in the agricultural, industrial, pharmaceutical and construction sectors of Azerbaijan. At the same time, Hungary can be seen as an entry into the Central European market for Azerbaijani products.

Agreements signed between SOCAR and MVM, MOL and other major Hungarian companies indicate the creation of a real economic model in the energy and industrial sectors. In addition, cooperation in the field of pharmaceutical production, space technologies and the creation of free economic zones is the beginning of the use of the technological potential of a friendly country in Azerbaijan [4].

Economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and Hungary has been developing rapidly in recent years. Both countries cooperate mutually beneficial, especially in the fields of energy, agriculture, transport and services. Azerbaijan, which has natural resources, modern transport infrastructure and a strategic geographical position, puts forward proposals in various fields that meet the economic interests of Hungary.

Economic relations, strategic partnership and friendship between the two countries are based on mutual respect and trust. As of the end of 2024, trade between our countries increased by 29 percent, which is a significant indicator of the strengthening and development of relations. This growth is due to the expansion of Azerbaijan's presence in European markets and the expansion of trade relations with Hungary.

In addition, the volume of foreign direct investment from Hungary to the Azerbaijani economy in 2024 amounted to 1.018 billion US dollars. This indicates Hungary's interest in the economy of Azerbaijan and the development of mutual investment relations between the two countries. Azerbaijani investors, in turn, invest heavily in agriculture, transport and other sectors of Hungary, which further strengthens the economic partnership [3].

This investment in the Hungarian economy is important not only in terms of financial resources, but also in terms of technological development and innovation in various fields. Such cooperation not only ensures economic growth, but also allows deepening strategic relations between countries and implementing new projects on a mutually beneficial basis.

Hungarian companies are interested in participating in the restoration and construction work carried out in the liberated territories. The KÉSZ group of companies is reconstructing the village of Soltanly, Jebrazil district. At the expense of the Hungarian government, buildings for preschool and general education institutions will be built in the village of Soltanly. Hungarian companies traditionally participate in the Azerbaijan international exhibitions "Reconstruction, Restoration and Development of Karabakh" - "Rebuild Governance" held in Baku.

Meetings of the Joint Commission on Economic Cooperation between the Governments of Azerbaijan and Hungary are held annually. Joint business forums are regularly organized in the capitals of both countries. The last, 11th meeting of the Joint Commission was held in Budapest in June 2025.

Important steps have been taken to develop cooperation in the industrial sphere. On July 10, 2023, a joint venture agreement was signed between Azerbaijan Investment Company OJSC and the Hungarian company Hell Energy, and on July 31, an agreement on the joint production of pharmaceuticals in Azerbaijan between Scandens Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd LLC and Gedeon Richter. On April 24, 2025, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed between Azerkosmos and 4iG Space and Defense Ltd. Also in January 2022, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed between the Alyat Free Economic Zone and the Hungarian Export Promotion Agency [6].

There are also ample opportunities for developing cooperation in the field of agriculture. In 2023 and 2024, mutual visits of the Ministers of Agriculture of Azerbaijan and Hungary took place.

The development of bilateral relations in the field of military and defense industry is of mutual interest. In 2023 and 2024, mutual visits of the defense ministers of Azerbaijan and Hungary took place. Hungary was represented by the national pavilion at the 5th Azerbaijan International Defense Exhibition "ADEX-2024" and the 14th International Exhibition of Internal Security, Protection and Rescue Means "Securex Caspian," held in Baku on September 24-26, 2024.

Education and humanitarian relations: the basis of the future

Azerbaijani-Hungarian relations are strengthened not only by political and economic, but also by historical and cultural ties. The creation by Hungary of educational opportunities for hundreds of Azerbaijani students within the framework of the Stipendium Hungaricum program, the installation of a bust of Nizami Ganjavi in Hungary, the opening of cultural centers at the Azerbaijan University of Languages show that cooperation is strategic and at the cultural and humanitarian level.

The Embassy of Azerbaijan in Hungary translates, publishes and distributes books on the history, literature and culture of our country into Hungarian. Concerts are organized with the participation of famous musicians. Cooperation is also developing in the field of education; relations between universities of the two countries have been established, joint projects are being implemented. These are sincere steps aimed at deepening the

integration and rapprochement of peoples. Such an atmosphere is the basis of both cultural diplomacy and long-term mutual respect.

In connection with the announcement of Shushi as the "Cultural Capital of the Turkic World," and Veszprem as the "Cultural Capital of Europe" for 2023, on January 30 of the same year, a "Memorandum of Understanding was signed to establish friendly relations and cooperation in the field of culture, tourism, urban planning, science, economy and other spheres of public life between Shusha, Republic of Azerbaijan, and Veszprem, Republic of Hungary."

The level of humanitarian cooperation between the two countries is currently satisfactory. Hungarian students are also allocated educational scholarships under the Intergovernmental Scholarship Program. Currently, up to 700 Azerbaijani students study in Hungary.

On October 19, 2023, the opening of the bust of the great Azerbaijani poet and thinker Nizami Ganjavi took place in the Hungarikum park in Lakitelek (Hungary).

The Hungarian Language and Culture Center operates at the Azerbaijan University of Languages. On May 19, 2025, the Center for Azerbaijani Language and Culture was opened at the Lorand Eötvös University (ELTE), one of the leading universities in Hungary [5].

Direct scheduled flights operated by Wizz Air between the two capitals contribute to the expansion of tourist links.

Bridge between the Turkic world and Europe

The activities of the Representative Office of the Organization of Turkic-Speaking States in Budapest and the observer status of Hungary in this organization are also of particular importance from the point of view of cultural and political cooperation. Prime Minister Viktor Orban and Minister of Foreign Affairs and Foreign Trade Peter Siyarto have repeatedly stated that Hungary is both the easternmost state in Europe and the westernmost state in the Turkic world.

In July 2024, Viktor Orban visited Shusha to participate in the informal Summit of Heads of State of the Organization of Turkic States. The adopted Karabakh Declaration noted the valuable contribution of Hungary to the work of the OTG as an observer.

On May 21, 2025, an informal Summit of the Heads of State of the Organization of Turkic States was held in the Hungarian capital Budapest, where it was noted that Hungary intends to play the role of a bridge between Europe and the Turkic world, and Azerbaijan is an important player at the origins of this bridge. At this Summit, President Ilham Aliyev stated that "This is our family" and the inclusion of a non-Turkish state such as Hungary in the ranks of this family strengthens the inclusive strength of the organization and its potential for influence [1].

Conclusion

The "Law on the Protection of Sovereignty," adopted by Hungary in 2023, reflects the spirit of resistance to foreign interference in the country's political

system. It is noteworthy that the philosophy of this law also coincides with the policy pursued in Azerbaijan aimed at independent decision-making and maintaining internal stability. This rapprochement is important in terms of the compatibility of the political values of the two countries. Increasing institutional resilience to external influences is an important factor in protecting the strategic independence of both countries.

Azerbaijani-Hungarian relations are no longer limited to cooperation, but become a multifaceted alliance that ensures mutual strategic interests. This alliance serves as an example of stability, development and sustainable partnership not only for the two countries, but for the entire region. Joint participation in such global events as COP29, cooperation in the field of energy, transport, culture, defense and law, outlines the contours of a new geopolitical model.

This cooperation strengthens both Azerbaijan's influence in Europe and Hungary's ties with the Turkic world. This partnership model can become the basis for the creation of wider regional blocs in the future - on the outskirts of Europe, in the Turkic world.

In general, Azerbaijani-Hungarian relations are developing in line with the strategic goals of both countries and can lead to the emergence of new models of partnership in the international arena. This cooperation plays an important role not only in ensuring the security of the two countries, but also in the broader regional and global context, as well as in resolving energy issues.

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